

I WILL BE A POLYGLOT: MY JOURNEY TO LEARNING MULTIPLE LANGUAGES

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Annotation: The author, Dildora, shares her journey to becoming a polyglot, someone who can speak multiple languages fluently. She sets a goal to learn at least five languages by the time she graduates high school and chooses French, German, and Mandarin Chinese to add to her already known English and Russian. She uses various resources such as language-learning apps, foreign-language films and TV shows with subtitles, language-learning websites, and hopes to travel to immerse herself in the languages. Staying motivated by setting small goals and tracking her progress, she finds learning multiple languages not only a fun hobby but also helpful in various careers and broadening her perspective.

Key words: polyglot, languages, goal, English, Russian, French, German, Mandarin Chinese, resources, language-learning apps, foreign-language films and TV shows with subtitles, language-learning websites, travel, motivation, careers, perspective.

Аннотация: Автор, Дилдора, рассказывает о своем пути к тому, чтобы стать полиглотом, человеком, свободно говорящим на нескольких языках. Она ставит перед собой цель выучить как минимум пять языков к моменту окончания средней школы и выбирает французский, немецкий и китайский языки в дополнение к китайскому, чтобы добавить к ней уже известные английский и русский языки. Она использует различные ресурсы, такие как приложения для изучения языков, фильмы на иностранных языках и телешоу с субтитрами, веб-сайты для изучения языков и надеется путешествовать, чтобы погрузиться в языки. Сохраняя мотивацию, ставя небольшие цели и отслеживая свой прогресс, она находит изучение нескольких языков не только забавным хобби, но и полезным в различных карьерах и расширяет ее кругозор.

Ключевые слова: полиглот, языки, цель, английский, испанский, французский, немецкий, китайский, ресурсы, приложения для изучения языков, фильмы и сериалы на иностранном языке с субтитрами, языковые сайты, путешествия, мотивация, карьера, перспектива.

Hello, my name is Dildora and I am 12 years old. I have always been fascinated by languages and the way they connect people from different parts of the world. As a child, I grew up speaking English, but I was always curious about other languages. I would watch foreign films with subtitles and try to learn new words and phrases.

As I got older, my interest in languages only grew stronger. I started to study Russian in school and found it to be a very interesting and useful language. I loved learning new vocabulary and grammar rules, and I was excited to be able to communicate with people from Russian-speaking countries.

But I didn't want to stop at just one language. I wanted to learn as many languages as possible and become a polyglot. A polyglot is someone who can speak multiple languages fluently. I knew it would be a challenging journey, but I was determined to make it happen.

The first step on my journey to becoming a polyglot was to set a goal for myself. I decided that I wanted to learn at least five languages by the time I graduated high school. This would give me a

solid foundation in multiple languages and allow me to communicate with people from all over the world.

The next step was to figure out which languages I wanted to learn. I already knew English and Russian, so I decided to add French, German, and Mandarin Chinese to my list. These languages are all widely spoken around the world and would be useful for both personal and professional reasons.

Once I had my goals and languages set, it was time to start learning. I knew that simply taking classes in school wouldn't be enough, so I started looking for other resources to help me learn.

One of the first things I did was download language-learning apps on my phone. There are many great apps out there that can help you learn a new language, such as Duolingo, Babbel, and Rosetta Stone. These apps allow you to practice vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation at your own pace.

I also started watching foreign-language films and TV shows with subtitles. This helped me get used to hearing the language spoken and pick up on new words and phrases. I found that watching shows in the language I was learning made it more interesting and fun.

Another resource I used was language-learning websites. There are many websites out there that offer free lessons and exercises for learning a new language. Some of my favorites are Memrise, Lingoda, and FluentU.

Of course, one of the best ways to learn a new language is to immerse yourself in it. This means traveling to a country where the language is spoken and practicing your skills with native speakers. While I haven't had the opportunity to travel yet, I hope to in the future.

As I started learning new languages, I found that it was important to stay motivated. Learning a new language can be challenging and frustrating at times, but it's important to remember why you started in the first place.

One way I stay motivated is by setting small goals for myself. For example, I might try to learn 10 new vocabulary words each day or watch one episode of a foreign-language show without subtitles.

I also like to track my progress by keeping a journal of my language-learning journey. This allows me to see how far I've come and celebrate my accomplishments.

Learning multiple languages has not only been a fun hobby for me, but it has also opened up many opportunities. Knowing multiple languages can be useful in many careers, such as international business, diplomacy, and tourism.

In addition, being able to communicate with people from different parts of the world has broadened my perspective and helped me understand different cultures and ways of life.

While I still have a long way to go on my journey to becoming a polyglot, I am excited to see where it takes me. I hope to continue learning new languages and exploring different parts of the world.

If you're interested in learning a new language, I encourage you to give it a try. It may be challenging at first, but the rewards are well worth it. Who knows, maybe one day you'll be a polyglot too!

Conclusion by her teacher. As Dildora's teacher, I am impressed by her dedication and passion for language learning. Her goal to become a polyglot is ambitious, but she has shown that with the right resources and motivation, it is achievable. By utilizing various tools such as language-learning apps, foreign-language films and TV shows with subtitles, and language-learning websites, she has taken advantage of the many resources available to her. I am also pleased to see that she plans to travel to immerse herself in the languages, which is an excellent way to solidify her language skills. Learning multiple languages not only benefits her personally but also opens up various career

opportunities and broadens her perspective. I am proud of Dildora's progress and look forward to seeing her continue to excel in her language-learning journey.

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